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Investigation into the Use of Clay and Carbonized Palm Kernel Shell Mixture as Water Filter

A.O. Oke and O.A. Abiola

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife, Nigeria

E-mail: okekola@oauife.edu.ng, okekola@yahoo.com

Abstract

Investigation was made into the effect of varying the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in clay/sand mixture. Different proportions of carbonized palm kernel shell were mixed with clay and the mixtures were used to mold slab samples for analysis and testing. Filter was formed from different mixing ratio of clay and carbonized palm kernel shell mixture using a fabricated mould and water was allowed to filter through them. Analysis of the different filtrates from the samples was carried out to determine some physical and chemical properties. The result of total solid, total hardness and magnesium hardness of sample A (10% carbon); total dissolved solid of sample B (20% carbon); and iron content of sample E (50% carbon) conform with the WHO's standards.

Keywords: Remote Sensing Clay; Sand; Palm kernel; Carbonized; Physical and chemical properties.

1.0 Introduction

Every living thing both large and small needs water to sustain life and pure water to guarantee it because water is necessary to life on earth, (Mendie, 2005). All organisms contain it; some live in it; some drink it. As revealed by John (2007), plants and animals require water that is pure, and they cannot survive if their water is loaded with toxic chemicals or harmful microorganisms. If severe, water pollution can kill large number of fish, birds, and other animals, in some cases killing all members of a group in an affected area. Water Pollution refers to contamination of streams, lakes, underground water, bays, or oceans by substances harmful to living things, which makes it unpleasant to look at, smell, and swim in. Even aquatic harvest from polluted waters may be unsafe as food. People who ingest polluted water can become ill, and with prolonged exposure, may develop cancers or bear children with birth defects.

Metcalf et al. (1991) highlighted the major water pollutants/contaminants as: dissolved solids (fixed and volatile), suspended solid (fixed and volatile), settle-able solid, biochemical oxygen demand, total organic demand, nitrogen (organic, free ammonia, nitrite and nitrate), phosphorus (organic and inorganic), chlorides, sulfate, alkaline (such as CaCO_3), total coliform, volatile organic compounds (VOCs). Lewis (1980) listed the major water pollutant as colour, odour, turbidity, pH, temperature, appearance, conductivity, nitrate, fluorides, iron, cobalt and vanadium, nickel, arsenic, cadmium, chromium, lead, selenium, mercury, barium, cyanide, sulphates, chloride, sodium, hardness, phosphates, ammonia, nitrites, phenols, polyaromatic hydrocarbon, total organic chlorine and other element such as potassium and aluminium. Mendie (2005) in his work enumerated water pollutant as iron, calcium, magnesium, aluminium, silica, zinc, arsenic, barium, chromium, sodium, lead, mercury, cadmium, asbestos, fluorides, chloride, nitrates/nitrites, Chlorobenzene, pesticides and radionuclides. Relmond (2006) categorized all water pollutants into: petroleum products, pesticides and herbicides, heavy metals, hazardous wastes, excess organic matter, sediments, infectious organism and thermal pollution. These pollutants are from various sources such as human activities, industrial activities, mining activities, animal actions and natural phenomenon (John, 2007; Wipo, 2006).

The process of removing pollutant from water can be classified as primary, secondary or tertiary treatment (Huang and Karadi, 2007; Metcalf et al., 1991). The primary treatment include: grit chamber removal, sedimentation, floatation, digestion, etc. The secondary treatment include: trickling filter, activated sludge and stabilization pond. The tertiary

treatment, also known as advanced waste treatment include: reverse osmosis, electrodialysis, ammonia stripping, de-nitrification, phosphate precipitation, chlorination and ozone treatment. The current work can be categorised under the primary pollutant removal. It is expected to be used where the source of water is free of harmful pollutants that cannot be removed by filtration and adsorption.

Adsorption is a process that occurs when a gas or liquid solute accumulates on the surface of a solid or a liquid (adsorbent), forming a molecular or atomic film (the adsorbate). It is different from absorption, in which a substance diffuses into a liquid or solid to form a solution. In this process active carbon is the solid. Activated carbon is produced specifically so as to achieve a very large surface area (between 500 - 1500 m²/g). Very large surface area makes active carbon ideal for adsorption. Active carbon comes in two variations: Powder Activated Carbon (PAC) and Granular Activated Carbon (GAC). The GAC version is mostly used in water treatment; it can adsorb the following soluble substances: mineral oil, BTEX, poly aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), (chloride) phenol, halogenated substance such as I, Br, Cl, H and F, odor, taste, yeasts, various fermentation products, non-polar substances (substances which are non soluble in water) (Metcalf and Eddy, 1991). Adsorption onto activated carbon of some water pollutant such as colours and odour has been found to be superior compared to other techniques (Hameed and Daud, 2008) and filtration has also been found to remove some other water pollutants such as total dissolved solid and other free particles (Hamoda et al., 2004). However, commercially available activated carbons are still considered expensive (Sonja et al., 2005), hence the experimentation on palm kernel shells. Palm kernel shell is an agricultural by product of palm tree which is found to be abundant in Nigeria (Owolarafe and Oni, 2011). Researchers have studied the production of activated carbons from different materials such as rubber seed coat, pecan shells, jute fibre, Indian rosewood sawdust, olive stones, pinewood, sawdust, coir pith, rice husk, bamboo, rattan sawdust and oil palm fibre (Hameed and Daud, 2008). Carbonized palm kernel shell is an activated carbon made from Palm kernel shell.

Because of the importance of portable water, there are huge challenges all over the world regarding the handling of surface water in order to preserve a sustainable future. Thus, it has become necessary to purify surface water to a certain level in order to make it safe for both human and aquatic animals, by removing the pollutants. This paper therefore aims at determining if clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell can remove water contaminants to World Health Organization's (WHO's) acceptable level. In other word, to compare water purified by clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell with the World Health Organization's (WHO's) standards. The peculiar feature of water purification is not only to process large volume of water to remove all kind of solid matter, including bacteria, but also that the operating cost must be optimally low (Purchas, 1971). Since water is a necessity to both plants and animals, it becomes very important that portable water is made readily available for usage. At the achievement of the aims of this work, there will be a reduction in the cost of purification of surface water. The disadvantages of chlorination highlighted in the work of Tortora and Funke, (1995) and Bergsrud et al., (2002) are also overcome. Clay, unless processed and add with proper percentage of sharp sand aggregate, will filter little or no water and the clay usually add more microorganism to the water. Clay minerals might be helpful in the removal of hazardous chemicals and the adsorption properties of activated carbon will further purify the water. In addition, natural clay minerals adsorb cations and non-charged hydrophilic compounds, but almost do not interact with anions and hydrophobic pollutants as most organic pollutants, including naphthalene and phenolic derivatives. By pre-treating clay minerals with a suitable organic cation, the surface properties of the adsorbent may be adapted, and fast sorption is observed, removing large amounts of such pollutants. Carbonized

palm kernel shell serves both as aggregate and a medium to remove taste, colour and odour but not microorganism from water (Droste, 2002). The use of clay in the purification of water has limitations. This is because chemical pollutants are present in water and are hazardous to human health and aquatic life (Rytwo et al., 2007). Thus, it is only essential to remove such pollutants from water and try to reduce their impact.

2.0 Experimental procedure

2.1 Raw materials

The major material used in the course of this work was clay which is obtained from Ife North Local Government area of Osun State, Nigeria; alongside sand which was also readily available. The mixture was heat treated to enhance its properties in the filtration of water. The other major important material was the activated carbon made from palm kernel shell. According to Oke and Omoleye (2006), clay-sand mixture with 90% clay and 10% sand of particle size of between 0.5mm to 1mm will best serve filtration purposes. This specification was adopted in the cause of this work, while carbon was varied from 10% up to 100% as it was added to clay/sand mixture. A control experiment was performed for ordinary carbon and also for 90% clay and 10% sand mixture.

2.2 Material preparation

The clay obtained in the raw form and the carbonized palm kernel shell was crushed separately to smaller particle by the use of hammer. The as-mined sand was washed and dried naturally to remove impurities. The dry ground clay was passed through a specify size in order to allow finer particles of the clay pass through the mesh leaving the coarser particles. The particles of the sand and carbonized palm kernel shell were also sieved separately to obtain homogenous mixture of clay and sand with carbonized palm kernel shell. A well sieve clay and sand were first measured and mixed in the ratio 10% to 90% by volume and ordinary carbon powder was also selected for the control experiment. The main experiment had carbonized palm kernel shell added to clay/sand mixture taking as a whole in the ratio 1:9, 2:8, 3:7, 4:6, 5:5, 6:4, 7:3, 8:2, 9:1 respectively, selected by volume. Each selected sample of clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell was mixed and blended together by piling the clay/sand mixture and the carbonized palm kernel shell into a cone-shaped dune and moving the pile while water was sprinkled.

2.3 Fabrication of the filter

A water filter is a device which removes impurity from water by means of a fine physical barrier, chemical process and or biological process. These filters were made of a square solid with cylindrical hole through the center and close at the other end. To facilitate this shape, a mould was prepared. The mould comprises of outer square shape with handles on opposite sides and the inner cylindrical shape place on a flat plate to facilitate its removal. The mould was made from metallic material 10 mm thickness, rather than wood which damage easily on compression since very high compression was required for mixing ratio of between 6:4 and 9:1 because of reduce plasticity effect of the clay. The paste from the clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell was then fashioned into the annular space between the inner cylindrical and the outer square shape mould and labeled A-J. Sample A contained 10% carbon, sample B contained 20% carbon and carbon content was increased arithmetically thus with common difference of 10% up to 100% carbon content for sample J. The filters so fabricated were of the size: length 100mm, breadth 100mm, height 50mm with 50mm diameter hole of depth 40mm. It has a bottom thickness of 10mm. The mould was removed after 48 hours and then the filter were allowed to cure properly in the sun for about two days. The samples were fired in a furnace at a temperature of 900°C. Various mechanical properties of water filter have

been investigated and presented by Oke and Omoleye (2006), their result was used as guide in the present work.

3.0 Results and Discussions

The results of the physical and chemical analysis that were carried out on the filtrate (water filtered through the filtrating medium) are discussed below.

3.1 Physical analysis of filtrate (water samples)

The physical analysis on the filtrate include: tests for appearance, pH value, total solid, total dissolved solid and suspended mater.

3.1.1 Appearance

The appearance also known as the colour for the samples, A – J are clear solution with brown sediments, Y is a clear solution with black spec and Z (raw water) is a clear solution with black particle sediments (refer to Table 1). The clear nature of the samples makes it conform with the WHO's standard.

3.1.2 pH Value

The pH value of the original water sample was 7.62. The clay-sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell have a little effect on the samples as shown in Figure 1. The WHO's standard fall between 6.5 - 8.5.

Figure 1: pH value against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.1.3 Total solids

The result of total solids for the original water sample was 364. For 100% carbon there is high level of reduction in total solid. With clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell, the values of total solid reduce with increase in carbon content as shown in Figure 2. The reason for the behaviour of the graph at 10% carbonized palm kernel shell is due to the fact that addition of little amount of carbonized palm kernel shell i.e. between 0 and 10% lead to existence of pores between the clay-clay particles, the pores reduces as the quantity of carbonized palm kernel shell increases. Also, this increase in carbonized palm kernel shell increases the rate of adsorption of some solid particles.

Figure 2: Total solids (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.1.4 Total Dissolved Solids

The result of total dissolved solid for the original water sample was 312. For 100% carbon there is high level of reduction in the value. With clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell the values reduces with increase carbon content. This is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Total dissolved solids (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.1.5 Suspended Matter

The minimum value obtained was 8 while the maximum value obtained was 52. Its content in water does not matter, since according to Schulz and Okun (1984), WHO’s standard can vary. The results of suspended matter are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Suspended matter (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2 Chemical analysis of filtrate (water samples)

The physical analysis on the filtrate include: tests for total acidity, total hardness, calcium hardness, magnesium hardness, chlorides, ammonical nitrogen, phosphate and iron.

3.2.1 Total Acidity

The result of total acidity for the samples including original water sample was 5 and 10 as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Total acidity (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2.2 Total Hardness

The result of total hardness for the original water sample is 28. There was no significant change in the result when only carbonized palm kernel shell was used. With mixture of clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell there was higher increase from the original value as shown in Figure 6. The result of sample A is closer to the WHO’s standard which is 250.

Figure 6: Total hardness (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2.3 Calcium Hardness

The result of calcium hardness for the original water sample is 8. The clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell does not have enough strength to raise the calcium hardness of the water samples to the WHO’s standard. The result of calcium hardness is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Calcium hardness (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2.4 Magnesium Hardness

The result of magnesium hardness for the original water sample was 8. The clay-sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell raises the magnesium hardness of the water samples above the WHO’s standard. The result of magnesium hardness is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Magnesium hardness (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2.5 Chlorides

Carbon alone has no effect on the chloride content of the water sample. The mixture of clay/sand mixture and carbonized palm kernel shell cannot also bring the chloride content in the water sample to the WHO’s acceptable standard of 250. Figure 9 show the results of the chloride content of the water samples.

Figure 9 Chlorides (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2.6 Ammonical Nitrogen

The effect of carbonized palm kernel shell and its mixture with clay/sand mixture had adverse effect on the ammonical nitrogen content of the water samples. The result of ammonical nitrogen content in the water samples are shown in Figure 10. The WHO's acceptable standard is shown in Table 1.

Figure 10: Ammonical nitrogen (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2.7 Phosphate

Carbonized palm kernel shell has higher effect on the phosphate content of the water sample as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Phosphate (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2.8 Iron

The result of calcium hardness for the original water sample was 0.19. The result remains the same in water samples gotten from higher percentages of carbonized palm kernel shell. The result of sample E with 50% carbon is reasonable compare to the WHO's standard.

Figure 11: Iron (ppm) against the percentage of carbonized palm kernel shell in the clay/sand mixture

3.2 Comparism of WHO’s standard with our result

For the safety of human beings around the globe, the World Health Organization has set a standard that must be maintained in water before its consumption. The set up standard by WHO as shown in Table 1, warranted the need for water to be treated before their consumption

Table 1: Comparism of WHO’s standard with our result raw water

Parameter	WHO’s standard	(Z) Raw water
Appearance	Clear	clear
p ^H value	6.5 – 8.5	7.62
Total solid	500	364
Total dissolve solid	<500	312
Suspended matter	Variable	52
Total hardness	250	28
Calcium hardness	200	8
Magnesium hardness	150	20
Iron	0.30	0.19
Chloride	250	53.25
Ammonical nitrogen	0.05	0.18

Source: Schulz and Okun (1984)

5.0 Conclusion

Results of physico-chemical analysis of the water samples show that the appearance and pH value of all the samples were in other, so also is suspended matter whose value can vary with respect to the WHO’s standards. It can be seen that the result of total solid, total hardness and magnesium hardness of sample A (10% carbon); total dissolved solid of sample B (20% carbon); and iron content of sample E (50% carbon) conform with the WHO’s standards. All the samples had no meaningful effect on the chloride and ammonical nitrogen content of the water sample. On a general note the result of sample A (10% carbon) is better when compare with the WHO’s standards.

For water to be safe for human consumption, not only must the physico-chemical analyses meet up with the WHO’s standard, the microbiology analysis must also meet up, so microbiological analysis should be carried out on water samples.

References

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